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Gravimetric Determination of Platinum with P-Dimethylaminoanil of 3-Phenanthryl Glyoxal

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IN our previous communication¹, chelates of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pt(IV), Mn(II) and Fe(III) with *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-Phenanthryl glyoxal (ligand) have been prepared and characterised. It has been observed that ligand forms dark coloured chelates which are more or less soluble in acetone except Pt(IV) chelate. Ligand reacts quantitatively with Pt(IV) in acetone to give light grey precipitate. It is therefore thought worthwhile to carry gravimetric estimations of Pt(IV) with the ligand and to note the effect of various compounds present.

Preparation of the solutions: Reagent (*p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal²) was dissolved in acetone to prepare approximately 0.01M solution. Stock solution of H₂PtCl₆.6H₂O was prepared in acetone and standardised gravimetrically by the procedure described by Vogel³.

A known volume (2–65 ml) of platinum chloride was taken and diluted to 75–100 ml and the precipitant solution was added slowly with constant stirring; grey precipitate of platinum (IV) chelate is formed immediately. After allowing to stand for 15 min., the precipitate was filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed several times with dry acetone, dried in oven and weighed as Pt(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)Cl₄. Several experiments were performed by using different volumes of platinum chloride solution.

From the experimental results, it may be concluded that *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal can effectively be employed as a gravimetric

reagent for platinum. In the gravimetric experiments error found was of the order 1–2%. The precipitate is insoluble in 75% acetic acid acetone, ether, benzene and carbontetrachloride. *P*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal is tested as gravimetric reagent only for Pt(IV) in acetonic medium, hence this method may be regarded as of limited applicability. However, reagent is quite effective in 75% acetic acid medium also. Moreover, the reagent is quite specific in presence of nickel chloride, cupric chloride and bromide, cadmium chloride and acetate, ferric chloride, zinc chloride, manganese chloride and silver nitrate.

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Gravimetric Determination of Cadmium with the Ligand 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline

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THE ligand has recently been used for the gravimetric determination of Cu(II) by the authors. In the present investigation the same ligand has further been used for the gravimetric determination of cadmium. Investigations have indicated that at pH 7.5 to 10 of the ligand, it reacts with Cd²⁺ ions giving precipitate of insoluble metal complex. The cadmium complex after settling is of orange red or brown red colour. The element analysis shows that the mole ratio of the metal to ligand is 1 : 2. The method is useful even if 0.5 mg of cadmium is present.

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade and the ligand was prepared by the method of Bagulev and Elvidge¹.

Element Analysis—Ligand	%C	%H	%N
Found	58.9	3.9	17.5
Required	59.3	3.7	17.3

The following stock solns. were prepared.

- (1) 1-Imino-3-Thioisindoline...about 0.1% sodium salt soln. of the ligand in NaOH of pH 7.5 to 10.

(2) $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$...2.8 gm/lit containing small quantity of HNO_3 soln., found to contain 1.001 mg Cd^{2+} ions/ml.

Determination of Cadmium: A known volume of 1 to 50 ml of soln. No. 2 was taken and diluted (the amount of cadmium was not too much). A freshly filtered soln. No. 1 was added in excess. An orange red or brown red precipitate of cadmium complex was digested on a water bath for 20 min and filtered through a medium porosity sintered glass crucible. It was washed with water several times and then with ethanol, dried at 90° to 105° or in a vacuum dessicator and weighed as $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{S})_2$. The gravimetric factor for cadmium is 0.2585.

Element Analysis—Cd(Complex)	%C	%H	%N
Found	48.8	2.5	12.4
Required	48.4	2.3	12.8

TABLE 1

Determination of cadmium with the ligand

Sl.No.	mg. metal taken	mg. metal recovered	% Error
1	5	4.95	1.0
2	5	4.96	0.8
3	5	5.05	1.0
4	5	5.04	0.8
5	10	10.06	0.6
6	10	10.04	0.4
7	10	9.90	1.0
8	10	10.12	1.2
9	25	25.20	0.8
10	25	25.00	—
11	25	25.40	1.6
12	25	25.20	0.8

Interferences: There is generally no interference by the most common anions such as SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , CO_3^{2-} , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and CN^- . Only few cations interfere. These are $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Au}(\text{III})$, Pb , Ag , $\text{Hg}(\text{I})$, $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$, Bi , $\text{Pd}(\text{II})$, $\text{Pt}(\text{IV})$, Ni , Co , $\text{Rh}(\text{III})$, Tl , Ru .

Results and Discussion

The analytical data in table 1 indicate that the ligand can be effectively used as a promising gravimetric reagent for Cd in micro and semi-macro quantities. It is easy to bring the precipitate to a constant weight within 1 hr. The precision was fair and the accuracy was generally within the permissible limits.

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Studies in the Formation of Heterocyclic Rings containing Nitrogen : Part XVII Condensation of 4-Substitutedphenylenediamines with Acetylacetone

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IN our earlier communication¹, we reported the formation of N-(*o*-aminophenyl)2,5-dimethylpyrrole from *o*-phenylenediamine and acetylacetone.

In the present investigation the reaction between 4-substituted-*o*-phenylenediamines and acetylacetone was studied in detail to understand the effect of the substituent on the formation of the pyrrole derivatives (I or II) or a mixture of both. 4-chloro, 4-methyl and 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamines have been chosen for this study.

Equimolecular proportion of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine and acetylacetone were allowed to react in acetic acid at room temperature. The pure compound isolated from this reaction was found to have N-(*o*-aminoaryl)2,5-dimethyl-pyrrole structure based on its IR and NMR data (see Experimental). This product was identified as N-(2-amino-4-chlorophenyl)-2,5-dimethyl pyrrole (I = R = Cl)².

In a similar manner, 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine with acetylacetone yields a compound having N-(*o*-aminoaryl)2,5-dimethyl pyrrole structure. By comparison with N-(2-amino-4-methylphenyl) and N-(2-amino-5-methyl phenyl)-2,5-dimethyl pyrroles² the above product was found to be a mixture of both isomers (I & II, R = Me). GLC analysis using an authentic sample of I (R = CH_3) as reference compound showed that the present mixture consists of I and II (R = CH_3) in 3 : 2 proportion.

4-Nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine did not react with acetylacetone under similar conditions.

The formation of N-phenyl-2,5-dimethyl pyrrole in excellent yields from aniline and acetylacetone under identical conditions offers a palusible explanation to the present results. Compared to aniline